

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the sixth regular issue of 2022. First of all, I would like to welcome all the new members of our editorial board and also express my sincere gratitude to all the members who have recently retired. It is only thanks to the expertise of our editorial board and volunteer guest reviewers, as well as the generous support of the J.UCS consortium and the novel contributions of our authors, that we are able to maintain this high standard and even improve the impact factor over the years.

In this issue, various topical aspects of computer science are covered by 12 authors from 5 countries in 4 articles. Stefano Masneri, Ana Domínguez, Mikel Zorrilla, Mikel Larrañaga and Ana Arruarte from Italy present a systematic review of the literature on the use of augmented reality applications in primary and secondary schools, with a specific focus on collaborative, multi-user, and interactive applications. In their article, Julio Cesar Vale Neves, Luiz Enrique Zarate and Mark Alan Junho Song from Brazil describe an approach to add a new data structure, binary decision diagrams (BDD), to the TRIAS algorithm and retrieve triadic concepts for high dimensional contexts. In a collaborative research between Croatia and Ukraine, Igor Tomicic, Markus Schatten, and Vadym Shkarupylo propose an open ontology for self-sustainable human settlements in an effort to find a common language for modeling self-sustainable systems and address issues of heterogeneity of physical devices, protocols, software components, data and message formats, and other relevant factors for the implementation of smart systems. Last but not least, Derya Yiltas-Kaplan from Turkey presents her research on traffic optimization with software-defined network controllers.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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